

Yusupova Laylo Umidbek qizi
Bachelor, at Gulistan State University

Annotation: This article covers the peculiarities of spiritual and moral views in Iskhakhan Ibrat arars. His works also provide conclusions and suggestions on the peculiarities of spiritual and moral views.

Keywords: Hebrew works, spiritual and moral views, enlightened poet, pictographic writing.

It is known that the socio - political, educational movement that arose in Turkestan at the end of the XIX-beginning of the XX centuries brought enlightened individuals-jadids-to the stage of history. Among them are the people of qomusi knowledge such as mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdurauf Fitrat, Ubaydullohoja Asadullakhojayev, Abdullah Avlani. They sought to spend their knowledge on the path of prosperity of the nation, the development of society, did not spare their funds when the role came. Among them is a special place of Ibrat, the son of Ishaq Khan Junaydullahan, a representative of the Fergana jadidism movement.

An in-depth study of the invaluable heritage of our ancestors on a scientific basis is in constant attention. Incl. Mirziyoyev at a meeting with the voters of the Namangan region on November 2, 2016, as a symbol of reverence for the incomparable services of the great progressive and enlightened is'haqkhan Ibrat towards the spiritual and educational rise of our people, promoted the initiative to perpetuate his name, create a modern park, create a memorial complex and the “School of the sign”. Therefore, the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 13, 2017 “on the establishment of the atakli enlightened is'hogkhan Ibrat memorial complex in the Turaqrgan District of Namangan region” was adopted.

The son of is'hoq Khan Junaydullohoja, Ibrat was an enlightened poet, zabardast linguist, historian scholar, an early Uzbek printer, and was born in 1862 in the village of Toraqurghan near Namangan. He receives his initial education in the old school, and then in the hands of his mother. Later he went to Kokand and enrolled in madrasa. Is'hoq Khan Ibrat ends the madrasa in 1886 and returns to Toraqurghan. He began his career as an educator by spreading enlightenment in the village. That same year, it opens a new school that is quite different from the old local schools.

Is'hoq Khan Ibrat would go on a Hajj trip in 1887. He then continues his journey through the countries of the East. He visited Central European cities such as Istanbul, Sofia, Athens, Rome, settled in Jeddah for quite some time, lived in Bombay and Calcutta. Is'hoq Khan mastered Arabic, Persian, Indo-urdu and English, which were widely used there. He returned to his homeland in 1896 keldi. To ' had opened a new method School in raqrgan (1907), and had established a lithograph in his village called "Matbaai is'hoqiya" (1908). Isaq Khan AbRam actively participated in the opening of new schools, training of teachers, making women educated in science. In his poems ("history of the printing house", "masnawi on culture", "newspaper feature", "pen"), he exposed the indicents of local and choral officials ("Ilmi Ibrat", poetry collection, 1909).

In 1901, his "Dictionary sitta-alsina" ("six-language dictionary"), composed of Arabic, Persian, Hindi, Turkish, Uzbek and Russian, was printed. This dictionary was suddenly used as a

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guide in the study of Oriental and Russian languages in jadid schools. Is'hoqhan Ibrat created "Jome' ul-khutut" ("the writing complex") in 1912, a work devoted to the history of writing, with references to Latin, Greek, Chinese, Indian, Arabic, the origin of Cyrillic, the history of development, and his own printing press was printed in "Matbaayi is'hoqiya". Ibrat sincerely wanted his people to be learned, enlightened. Over the next 20 years, he wrote 14 scientific-historical, linguistic works. Compiled a collection of poems "Devoni Ibrat", a compilation of 30 years of poetic work. History of historiography Fergana," history of culture "and" Meson uz-modern "scientific works yaratdi. Is' haqkhan Ibrat "gazetteer of Turkestan province", "Sadoi Turkestan", "Sadoi Fergana" gaz. lariga's articles promoted science, enlightenment, and culture. Ibrat's life in recent years has been much more threatening. From 1935 he was removed from all positions. In April 1937, an elderly 75-year-old poet and educator is arrested.

Isaac Khan felt great responsibility for the creation of the scientific and historical works of Abram. Because he considers himself responsible for every line he writes. The future generation learns from each of his words his own attitude and vision of the era, the life of individuals. He was able to pay great attention to the biased assessment of historical events, information. It can be learned from this that the scientist studied in depth the works of a huge number of orientalists, which showed his positive influence on his work.

In his work "history of Fergana", Isaac Khan paid special attention to the description of the attitude of the Khan and the Beks to historical events. The author quotes the reasonable words of Abdusamad noyib, one of the ministers of amir Nasrullo, who came up with a proposal by the Emir of Bukhara Nasrullo in 1842 to oppose a notorious event in Kokand and make attempts to unite with the Kokand Khanate and prevent an impending Russian invasion. "Kholo Khoqand died a conqueror, Fergana is a great country, how many soldiers and sipohu treasure were spent, the coming of Russia in alhol is a local danger, if the Khan had been repented and put on the Ox, subject to Bukhara, and a property would have been a shield to the enemies who came to us," said, "As long as the word would have struck the emir with.

In his work "Ta'rihi Fergana", Isaac Abram gives a wide place to the Russian conquest of Central Asia and the tragedies it brought. Tries to interpret on the basis of data.

Ishaq Khan AbRam looked with great hope and confidence at the bright future of his people, the construction of a free and hur life. His scientific and historical works are undoubtedly a necessary moderate resource in the study of the history of our motherland. The work of the scientist "Ta'rihi Fergana " has great historical - cultural significance and is considered a valuable written monument of the Uzbek people. As he intended to rework the work, he did not publish it.

After describing what is the purpose of writing the work: "in Turkestan music, it is famous as Fergana, and this is the story of the Fergana with the lines" who passed through, even if the interpretation of lafz ilan mazkurdur and muni was in ancient times, and from whose side the existence of a building is not known to anyone, The history of the cities of Hoqand, Andijan and Hamangan, and the way of life of the settled people are also cited.

AbRam records that the period before him was created by many historiographical scholars. For example, Fergana cites many works to reveal who was built from the side. Therefore, the period from 1213 ah to the Holy One, when he was close to his time, is widely illuminated. Especially in parochialism during the March of Tsarist Russia to Turkestan, in addition to the successive alternation of rulers above the state and the clear opening of the era of the Lord, the author expresses his objectionable attitude to the political – social life of this period.

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As one of the most pressing issues after achieving independence, black left to our history will be objectively assessed and focused on wiping it. The works of several of our creators have been published. Ibrat's "Ta'rihi Fergana" went out of print under the 1991 "Heritage" series. This work of Ishaq Khan is based on a copy of his *Ssifa Oriental Science*, which was collated with the pen of Inayat Khan Turaqurgani, which is kept in the manuscript Treasury. Bobobekov and M. Prepared for publication by hasanias.

Ishaq Khan Ibrat did not publish the work as he intended to recycle it. That is why the meeting of certain shortcomings and defects in the work was indicated by those who prepared it for publication: the city of "Khokand" is based on the words "Khuk – kand", which attribute its building to the event of 1709. However, the city of "Khogand" was known by this name in the 10th century. The meaning corresponds to "good", "anecdotal".

There are also erroneous opinions about some histories of the Kokand Khanate in the work. For example, Muhammad Ali Khan was not governor from 1822 to 1842, but Khan from 1822 to 1841. He abdicated in November 1841, and his younger brother Mahmud sits on the Kokand throne. But Isaac does not write anything about it. Indeed, if we read the work and leaf through the books of history, their objections are appropriate.

It is also said that " in 1865 on the threshold of Tashkent, Mullo falsely stated that Alimkul died of his wounds, and there are some, less significant, shortcomings. But these shortcomings do not bring down the value of the work. In general, the work also records the correct account of events in terms of content.

Thus, it is clear from the activities of Ishaq Khan Ibrat that he was one of the enlightened, folk-minded personalities. All his activities, his writings, his poems were directly for the nation, for its bright future. He approached everything meticulously and was always in search. As a product of this feature, he had a deep knowledge of many areas: mechanics, technology, physics, engineering. These areas were also able to be widely promoted in practice.

The creation of " Ta'rihi Fergana " is considered one of the great works of the scientist. Together with the fact that we learn through this work the past of our people, what they have experienced, it also serves as a mirror of lesson for us.

Together with the fact that " history Fergana " is a scientific – historical work, it is also a work of art. Its-ideological-artistic significance is that the ancient Fergana and the Kokand socio – political atmosphere of the time in which he lived, literary life is vividly reflected using the means of artistic images. Excerpts from the taurix, the Martians, the mukhammas, the narrative and the epic in it further enhanced the artistry of the work. In parallel, the work also embodied several artistic features. In this work, Ishaq Khan Ibrat, together with his unbiased historiography talent, also showed the ability of poetry, adiblik, ethnography.

In conclusion, the work " history of Fergana " is considered a valuable resource in the study of history, the social, literary environment of that time. It is a work worth studying and analyzing not only from the point of view of a historian or literary critic, but also as a political scientist, folklorist, linguist, geographer, ethnographer.

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